

OBSTACLES TO EFFECTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION IN THE MODERN ERA

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Abstract: This article examines the challenges facing contemporary foreign language teaching. Despite advancements in technology and increased globalization, obstacles persist that hinder effective language acquisition. The paper delves into key problem areas, including inadequate foundational skills, diverse student needs, limited access to authentic materials, and the need for more collaborative learning environments. By analyzing these challenges, the article advocates for innovative pedagogical approaches that address the complexities of foreign language learning in the 21st century.

Key words:

Introduction

In an increasingly interconnected world, the ability to communicate effectively in multiple languages has become a valuable asset. Foreign language proficiency opens doors to academic, professional, and cultural opportunities, enriching personal lives and fostering global understanding. Yet, despite the undeniable importance of language learning, contemporary foreign language teaching faces significant obstacles.

While technology has revolutionized access to resources and information, traditional methods of instruction often fall short of meeting the diverse needs of today's students. Additionally, the pressure to achieve fluency in a limited timeframe can create undue stress and hinder genuine language acquisition.

This article explores the key challenges that confront foreign language educators and examines potential solutions. By understanding these obstacles and implementing innovative teaching strategies, we can empower students to achieve fluency and embrace the transformative power of language learning.

Foreign students pursuing natural science subjects face particular challenges in understanding specialized terminology. The curriculum often incorporates themed modules based on grammatical topics. Textbooks typically present new grammatical concepts followed by speech patterns, short texts, and dialogues that incorporate the new vocabulary. This allows students to observe how words transform in combination with various grammatical structures.

Foreign students often struggle to comprehend lecture material in specialized subjects after completing their preparatory programs. Several factors contribute to this:

1. Isolation: Pre-university training often isolates foreign students from native speakers of the target language.
2. Adaptation: Foreign students become accustomed to the slower pace and simplified language used in preparatory programs.
3. Immersion: Upon completion of preparatory studies, foreign students are fully immersed in a language environment that may not consider their national psychological characteristics, and university teaching methods can be drastically different from those in their home countries.

This article proposes effective strategies to prevent these communication difficulties during students' initial years at university. This article investigates the learning challenges faced by foreign students during pre-university training, particularly in both foreign language and vocational subjects. These challenges often hinder their success in subsequent university studies. The author examines the pedagogical approach of teachers, identifying common mistakes observed through monitoring how foreign students are instructed in preparatory departments.

The article focuses on classes in vocational subjects, emphasizing how the methods of delivering educational materials should be adjusted to better accommodate the needs of foreign students. This tailored approach aims to improve students' understanding of the subject-specific language and enable teachers to identify and address potential learning obstacles.

Increased global connectivity has opened doors to authentic learning materials. These include textbooks published in the target language countries, periodicals, videos, audio recordings by native speakers, and more. As a result, developing foreign language competence has become a primary objective in language education.

International collaboration further enhances language education. Educational institutions are actively participating in international projects, collaborating on training materials, developing online programs, hosting intercollegiate conferences, and sharing best practices.

The article highlights the potential of mass media – news programs, feature films, music programs, and youth programs – to motivate learning and improve foreign language skills.

Limited study hours at universities pose a significant challenge to developing essential skills for reading professional literature in a foreign language, particularly in non-language-focused programs.

Effectively developing these skills allows students to focus primarily on understanding the text's meaning. Researchers Zh.A. Suvorova and R.P. Milrud have extensively analyzed the challenges of foreign language learning, highlighting the need for foundational reading skills. They argue that shortcomings often stem from inadequate school-level instruction, leaving many college applicants unprepared for the demands of reading foreign language materials.

Graduates of specialized language schools typically demonstrate stronger speaking skills than reading skills. This observation aligns with our own experiences, where

students often struggle to engage effectively with foreign language texts. The foundation for "proper" reading should be established in school through "educational" reading exercises.

High school graduates should possess the ability to silently read simple texts on socio-political and popular science topics, along with adapted fiction containing up to 9% unfamiliar vocabulary. This involves developing skills such as:

- * Making inferences: Drawing conclusions based on the text.
- * Semantic synthesis: Combining different parts of the text to understand its overall meaning.
- * Semantic processing: Understanding the meaning of individual words and phrases.

These skills provide a solid foundation for developing professional reading skills. The University's Role in Developing Professional Reading Skills. Unfortunately, these skills are not always adequately developed in high school, requiring university teachers to either develop or refine them for professional reading. To effectively address this, we must first understand the specific purposes for which future specialists read professional literature.

Conclusion

The modern landscape of foreign language teaching presents a complex tapestry of opportunities and challenges. While technological advancements and globalization have opened doors to a wealth of resources and learning experiences, inherent obstacles persist, demanding innovative pedagogical approaches and a renewed focus on student-centered learning. This exploration of contemporary obstacles has revealed the need for:

By acknowledging these challenges and implementing effective strategies, educators can empower students to achieve fluency and proficiency in foreign languages. This ultimately enables them to navigate a globalized world, enriching their academic and professional pursuits and fostering cross-cultural understanding. The future of foreign language teaching lies in embracing

innovation, adapting to evolving learning needs, and fostering a passion for language acquisition.

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